

Clinical validation of a novel point-of-care diagnostic aid for early detection and monitoring of Alzheimer's Disease

The Clinical protocol of 2D-BioPAD, a Horizon Europe Framework Programme

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Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is the most common cause of dementia, with enormous financial and social burden on a global scale. An early and accurate AD diagnosis could offer significant benefits. Current screening procedures are expensive, invasive and their accessibility is limited to highly specialized clinics.

The EU-funded 2D-BioPAD project (GA 101120706) aims to develop a fast, easy-to-use, cost-effective, and reliable system to aid with the early diagnosis of AD. Measuring simultaneously five proteins AD biomarkers with a point of care system can be a valuable tool for AD diagnostics at primary care settings.

A multi-center clinical pilot study has been designed to test, evaluate and validate the developed system under real-world conditions in three European (Finland, Germany and Greece) clinical centers specialized in AD and dementia diseases. The study will be conducted in two stages, a retrospective and prospective observational stage, also including a feasibility step to identify optimal screening conditions. The study will enroll up to 300 participants within the continuum of AD to achieve objectives that span from analyzing the five plasma biomarkers to validating the performance of the 2D-BioPAD diagnostic aid against benchmarking equipment and under real-world clinical conditions, while receiving feedback from the healthcare professionals.

4 key words:

Alzheimer's Disease

Blood Biomarkers

Point of care

Prevention